

ANALYST | Multi-actor approach roadmap for implementing an integrated holistic impact assessment to accelerate Safe and Sustainable Design (SSbD) acceptance in the plastic value chain

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Plastic pollution is one of the most serious threats to humanity. In response, the European Union is promoting an approach to guide the innovation of materials like Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) towards a safer, circular economy. In this context, the ANALYST project emerges with the aim of accelerating the transition towards a safer and more sustainable plastic value chain. The project also seeks to enhance the existing knowledge of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework. The success of the project depends on the development of a multi-actor approach roadmap, which will be detailed here.

This study employs the multi-actor roadmap as a tool for collaborative strategic planning to guarantee the success of the project, and includes 6 key stages: First, detailed implementation guidelines offer clear instructions and success metrics, while continuous monitoring facilitates ongoing enhancements. Tailored training programmes, the second component, boost team capabilities. Thirdly, a small-scale pilot test involving industrial organisations (multi-actors) from the PVC value chain is conducted to identify issues with the integrated approach. Feedback from this test and stakeholder consultations refines the approach. Lastly, the findings and the validated roadmap are disseminated to promote adoption and underscore the benefits, aiming to broaden its usage and support.

To start, stakeholders will receive guidelines to test the innovative integrated approach. Through tailored training, they will examine conventional materials that incorporates the 4 dimensions (health, environmental, economic, and social) aligned with the SSbD framework. Subsequently, these stakeholders will specify the requirements they wish to evaluate to foster innovations. Following this, insights and actions will be gathered to provide a comprehensive analysis of lessons learned, gaps, and risks. This analysis will serve to enhance both the integrated approach and the SSbD framework, while also providing critical feedback to develop strategies for extending the SSbD framework beyond the project's duration. It is important to mention that the proposed roadmap is not static, needing several iteration cycles to fully develop the final vision.

This roadmap is called to be a pivotal tool in ensuring the success of the ANALYST project, and involving various stakeholders, that will play a crucial role in facilitating the transition towards a safer and more sustainable plastic value chain.